

Synthesis and characterization of manganese(II) complexes derived from 2-substituted benzaldehyde semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : The metal complexes of manganese(II) with 2-chlorobenzaldehyde/2-ethoxybenzaldehyde semicarbazone (cbse, ebse) and thiosemicarbazone (cbtsc, ebtsc) have been synthesized and characterized by means of various physico-chemical techniques viz. elemental analysis, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies. IR spectral studies showed bidentate chelating behaviour of the ligands coordinating through azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen/thio keto sulphur atoms. Magnetic moment of these complexes indicates high spin configuration. The probable structure for all the complexes is proposed here.

Keywords : Semicarbazone, manganese(II), thiosemicarbazone, synthesis, complex, benzaldehyde.

Introduction

In the recent years, the study of semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone compounds has received great impetus attribute to perhaps to their remarkable potential in inhibiting ribonucleotide reductase, an obligatory enzyme in DNA synthesis^{1,2}. As a consequence, compounds containing these pharmacophores have been evaluated for their antiproliferative properties against a variety of tumors^{3,4}. Besides the antitumor activities, these compounds have also been shown to possess antimalarial⁵, bacteriocidal and fungicidal^{6,7}, antiviral⁸ and antitubercular⁹ activities. Thiosemicarbazones have been a subject of interest in the recent decades due to their variable applications in industries and analytical chemistry¹⁰. We report here the synthesis of some complexes of semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde and 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde with manganese(II) ion. These complexes have been characterized by means of various physico-chemical techniques viz. elemental analysis, magnetic moment, IR spectral and electronic spectral studies.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are highly stable under laboratory conditions and can be stored for a long period in a desiccator. The analytical data (Table 1) of all the complexes confirm to 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometric ratio corresponding to the general composition MnL_2X_2 (L = cbse, ebse, cbtsc and ebtsc; X = Cl^- , Br^- and $\frac{1}{2} SO_4^{2-}$). Synthesized metal complexes are insoluble in water but are ap-

preciably soluble in DMSO and DMF.

Infrared evidences :

A comparative scrutiny of the IR spectral data of complexes with those of free ligands gave clues regarding the donor sites of the ligand molecules. The absence of bands above 3400 cm^{-1} or in the region $2500\text{--}2600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which would be due to $\nu(O-H)$ and $\nu(S-H)$ vibrations respectively suggests the ligands exist in the keto/thione form¹¹. The IR spectral bands at $\sim 3015\text{--}3030$, ~ 1610 and $\sim 745\text{--}760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu(C-H)$, $\nu(C=C)$ and *ortho*-substitution vibrations respectively and are suggestive for aromatic character¹² of the ligands. The IR spectral band of the free ligands in the region $3370\text{--}3125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu(NH)$ and $\nu(NH_2)$ stretching vibrations¹³ and remain practically unaltered or shifted to higher wave number side suggesting no involvement in coordination. The strong band at $\sim 1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $\nu(C=O)$ stretching vibration¹⁴ while the band at $\sim 1532\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned due to $\nu(C=N)$ stretching vibration¹⁴. IR spectral bands of medium intensity at $\sim 995\text{--}1000$ and $\sim 815\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to $\nu(N-N)$ and $\nu(C=S)$ vibrations^{14,15}. The IR data of all the complexes reveal that the $\nu(C=S)$ is shifted to the lower region suggesting the sulphur atom is involved in the complexation with the metal ion. Shifting of characteristic absorption bands of ligands on complexation shows that the ligands behave in the bidentate fashion in all the manganese(II) complexes. The strong bands observed at $\sim 1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shift to lower wave num-

Note

Table 1. Elemental analysis data of manganese(II) complexes

Complexes	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
		Mn	C	H	N
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂) ₂ Cl ₂	Light pink	10.38 (10.34)	44.48 (44.36)	4.86 (4.81)	15.51 (15.53)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂) ₂ Br ₂	Dull camel	8.93 (8.88)	38.17 (38.10)	4.19 (4.13)	13.36 (13.33)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂) ₂ SO ₄	Camel	9.81 (9.88)	42.49 (42.41)	4.52 (4.59)	14.87 (14.82)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS) ₂ Cl ₂	Light green	9.80 (9.76)	41.81 (41.89)	4.55 (4.54)	14.60 (14.66)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS) ₂ Br ₂	Cream	8.50 (8.45)	36.21 (36.26)	3.98 (3.93)	12.79 (12.69)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS) ₂ SO ₄	Pink	9.33 (9.36)	40.19 (40.14)	4.30 (4.35)	14.14 (14.05)
Mn(C ₈ H ₈ N ₃ OCl) ₂ Cl ₂	Pale yellow	10.88 (10.72)	36.71 (36.79)	3.19 (3.07)	16.03 (16.09)
Mn(C ₈ H ₈ N ₃ OCl) ₂ SO ₄	Yellow	10.28 (10.23)	35.20 (35.10)	3.00 (2.93)	15.30 (15.36)
Mn(C ₈ H ₈ N ₃ SCl) ₂ Cl ₂	Light green	10.01 (10.10)	34.79 (34.66)	2.98 (2.89)	15.07 (15.16)
Mn(C ₈ H ₈ N ₃ SCl) ₂ SO ₄	Green blackish	9.79 (9.66)	33.11 (33.16)	2.88 (2.76)	14.55 (14.51)

ber side by about 35–60 cm⁻¹ in all the metal complexes indicating the participation of oxygen atom in complexation. The band at ~1532 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=N) stretching¹⁴ shift to lower wave number side by about 40–65 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen atom in coordination. The appearance of new bands at ~450 and ~520 cm⁻¹ are probably arising from ν(M–N) stretching vibrations¹⁶. IR spectra

of sulphate complexes show bands at ~1127, ~1048, ~1015 and ~891 cm⁻¹ indicating the bidentate nature of sulphate group¹⁷.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectral studies :

All the complexes under study show the magnetic moments at room temperature are in the range of 5.94–6.01 B.M. (Table 2) very close to spin only value corresponding to five unpaired electrons at the room tempera-

Table 2. Electronic spectral bands and magnetic moment of Mn^{II} complexes

Complexes	ν ₁ (cm ⁻¹) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (⁴ G)	ν ₂ (cm ⁻¹) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (⁴ G)	ν ₃ (cm ⁻¹) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (⁴ D)	ν ₄ (cm ⁻¹) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (⁴ P)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
Mn(ebsc) ₂ Cl ₂	18650	24200	28230	30965	5.94
Mn(ebsc) ₂ Br ₂	18880	24800	28910	30794	6.01
Mn(ebsc) ₂ SO ₄	18455	24700	28270	30440	5.91
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	18470	24360	28708	30850	5.97
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ Br ₂	18710	24500	28395	30790	6.00
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ SO ₄	18625	24594	28240	30470	5.95
Mn(cbsc) ₂ Cl ₂	18470	24275	28550	30775	5.94
Mn(cbsc) ₂ SO ₄	18590	24348	28232	30568	5.98
Mn(cbtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	18725	24805	28568	30495	6.01
Mn(cbtsc) ₂ SO ₄	18900	24906	28480	30600	5.97

Table 3. The molar extinction values (ϵ_{\max}) of corresponding to the wave number of the peaks as obtained in the electronic spectra of the complexes^a are given in the table

Compd. ^b	I (ϵ_{\max})	II (ϵ_{\max})	III (ϵ_{\max})	IV (ϵ_{\max})
Mn(ebsc) ₂ Cl ₂	536 (18400)	413 (24000)	354 (21000)	323 (29100)
Mn(ebsc) ₂ Br ₂	530 (18900)	403 (25000)	346 (21800)	325 (28800)
Mn(ebsc) ₂ SO ₄	542 (18000)	405 (24800)	354 (21200)	329 (28000)
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	541 (18000)	411 (24400)	348 (21800)	324 (28900)
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ Br ₂	534 (18600)	408 (24600)	352 (21600)	325 (29000)
Mn(ebtsc) ₂ SO ₄	537 (18400)	407 (24800)	354 (21300)	328 (28500)
Mn(cbsc) ₂ Cl ₂	541 (18100)	412 (24500)	350 (21500)	325 (28700)
Mn(cbsc) ₂ SO ₄	538 (18200)	411 (24500)	354 (21000)	327 (28700)
Mn(cbtsc) ₂ Cl ₂	534 (18500)	403 (24800)	350 (21700)	328 (28600)
Mn(cbtsc) ₂ SO ₄	529 (18900)	402 (25000)	351 (21700)	327 (28800)

^aThe spectral maxima in nm and the (ϵ_{\max}) values (in parentheses) in M⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

^bConcentration 10⁻⁴ M.

ture for high spin, six coordinated octahedral configuration¹⁸.

The electronic spectral bands for Mn^{II} complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones ligands lie in the region 18455–18900 cm⁻¹ (ν_1), 24200–24906 cm⁻¹ (ν_2), 28230–28910 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) and 30440–30965 cm⁻¹ (ν_4). These spectral bands are assigned as ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4P)$ transitions respectively and are characteristic for six coordinated octahedral stereochemistries^{17,19}.

Based on the observations of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, IR and electronic spectral studies, six coordinated octahedral geometry is suggested for all the complexes of manganese(II) under study.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical reagent grade. Electronic spectra were recorded in ethanol on Shimadzu UV and visible spectrophotometer 1601 C.P. while magnetic moment of the complexes were determined by Guoy's method using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. The IR spectra of the ligands and their complexes were scanned on Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR automatic recording spectrophotometer in potassium bromide. The analysis of C, H and N were done by microanalytical techniques. Metal content were estimated²⁰ by precipitating metal extract in dilute hydrochloric acid with diammonium hydrogen phosphate.

Synthesis of ligands :

The ligands 2-chlorobenzaldehyde/2-ethoxybenzal-

dehyde semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone were synthesized following by the literature²¹ by refluxing the semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide with 2-chlorobenzaldehyde and 2-ethoxybenzaldehyde respectively and confirmed by elemental analysis and IR spectral data.

General method for the preparation of metal complexes :

A hot aqueous ethanolic solution (20 ml) of metal salt (0.05 mol) was mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the respective ligands (10 mol) in a molar ratio of 1 : 2. The contents were refluxed for about 4–5 h. On cooling the contents, the coloured complexes separated out. The product obtained were filtered, washed with 50% ethanol, dried in the electric oven, analyzed and the analytical data are represented in Table 1.

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